

CODEN [USA]: IAJPBB

ISSN : 2349-7750

**INDO AMERICAN JOURNAL OF
PHARMACEUTICAL SCIENCES**

SJIF Impact Factor: 7.187

Available online at: <http://www.iajps.com>

Review Article

A REVIEW ON ALCOHOL INDUCED HEPATITIS***Mr. M. Akhil, Dr. C. Bhuvaneshwar Rao, Dr. K. Venugopal**¹Final Year B pharmacy, Krishna Teja Pharmacy College, Tirupati-517506.²Associate Professor, Department of Pharmacology Krishna Teja Pharmacy College, Tirupati-517506.³Professor and Principal, Krishna Teja Pharmacy College, Tirupati-517506.**Abstract:**

About one-third of those with extensive histories of high alcohol consumption develop alcoholic hepatitis. High short-term mortality, financial strain, and hospital resource use are all linked to it. When alcohol use disorder is present, alcoholic hepatitis, a potentially fatal consequence of alcohol addiction, usually manifests as hepatitis symptoms and indicators. A liver biopsy is necessary for the final diagnosis, albeit this is usually not necessary. The most serious clinical manifestation of alcoholic liver disease is alcoholic hepatitis. Abstinence is the primary means of recovery for alcoholic hepatitis, which has a bad prognosis in the absence of an appropriate pharmaceutical treatment. Since alcohol use disorders are becoming more widespread, alcoholic hepatitis's effects on society and medical expenses are predicted to rise sharply. While recent advancements in the pathophysiology of alcoholic hepatitis are promising and may lead to new treatment approaches, it is important to emphasize a multidisciplinary approach that takes into account the prompt detection and management of liver-related complications, infectious and metabolic diseases, malnutrition, and addiction counselling. In addition to appropriate candidate selection, transplant programs should offer sufficient post-transplant addiction care to make early liver transplantation for alcoholic hepatitis the most sobering experience in the upcoming ten years.

Keywords: Alcoholic Hepatitis, Alcoholic Liver Disease, Addiction, Corticosteroids, Liver Transplantation.

Corresponding author:**M. Akhil,**

Final Year B pharmacy,

Krishna Teja Pharmacy College, Tirupati-517506.

QR code

Please cite this article in press M. Akhil et al., *A Review On Alcohol Induced Hepatitis*., Indo Am. J. P. Sci, 2024; 11 (11).

INTRODUCTION:

In the US, excessive alcohol usage ranks as the third most common preventable cause of mortality [1]. Young people have a disproportionately high rate of alcohol-related mortality. Each alcohol-related death results in the loss of about 30 years of life, or 2.3 million years of potential life lost in the US in 2001. Drinking too much alcohol is linked to a number of health risks, including short- and long-term liver damage, various cancers, unintentional accidents sustained at work or while driving, personal and social violence, divorce, and strained social and familial ties. The risk of developing cirrhosis rises proportionately when one consumes more than 30 grams of alcohol daily; 120 grams or more is linked to the highest risk [2].

The point prevalence of cirrhosis is as high as 5.7% in individuals who consume 120 g of alcohol per day, compared to 1% in those who drink 30 to 60 g daily. Numerous forms of liver damage can result from long-term alcohol consumption. Alcoholic fatty liver can be cured through abstinence, although steatosis increases the risk of cirrhosis and hepatic fibrosis in those who persist in drinking [3]. The curable form of alcoholic liver disease called alcoholic hepatitis is the subject of this review. Appropriate diagnosis and treatment are crucial because up to 40% of patients with severe alcoholic hepatitis pass away within six months of the clinical condition beginning. A clinical manifestation of jaundice and liver failure known as alcoholic hepatitis typically develops after decades of severe alcohol consumption (mean intake of about 100 g per day).

Men are more likely than women to drink excessively and to suffer from alcoholic liver disease, despite the fact that female sex is not a risk factor in and of itself for alcoholic hepatitis [4]. Alcoholic hepatitis risk does not seem to be influenced by the type of alcohol used. The prevalence was almost 20% in a cohort of 1604 alcoholic patients who had liver biopsies; the incidence is unknown. The main indication of alcoholic hepatitis is the quick onset of jaundice, Fever, ascites, and loss of proximal muscle are other common symptoms. Individuals experiencing encephalopathy may have severe alcoholic hepatitis.

Typically, the liver is enlarged and painful. Laboratory investigations typically show that blood levels of alanine aminotransferase are lower and serum levels of aspartate aminotransferase are typically more than twice the upper limit of the normal range, though seldom exceeding 300 IU per millilitre. There is an elevated amount of serum creatinine, this is concerning since it often indicates the impending development of hepatorenal syndrome and mortality [5]. Hepatocellular damage caused by inflated (swollen) hepatocytes, typically including amorphous eosinophilic inclusion bodies known as Mallory bodies (also called alcoholic hyaline), surrounded by neutrophils, is revealed by microscopy in individuals with alcoholic hepatitis [6]. One defining lesion of alcoholic hepatitis is intrasinusoidal fibrosis, or fibrosis seen in the gap between the endothelial cell and the hepatocyte. Alcoholic fibrosis's characteristic symptoms, including as cirrhosis, periportal fibrosis, and perivenular fibrosis, frequently coincide with the signs of alcoholic hepatitis. A bad prognosis is indicated by the start of renal failure or by ongoing jaundice. Unfortunately, recovery from alcoholic hepatitis is not assured, even in cases where patients follow all medical care guidelines [7]. Many histologic characteristics associated with alcoholic hepatitis are also present in non-alcoholic steatohepatitis, a disorder linked to obesity and insulin resistance. These findings include inflated hepatocytes, steatosis, macroglobulin bodies, inflammation, intrasinusoidal collagen, and fibrosis or cirrhosis. Alcoholic liver disease (ALD) causes 64,000 hospital admissions and 1000 deaths annually in Australia [8]. Alcoholic hepatitis, alcoholic cirrhosis, and steatosis (alcoholic fatty liver) are among the overlapping spectrum of pathological processes that make up alcoholic liver disease. Additionally, the prevalence and burden of alcoholic liver disease have increased and are projected to do so in the years to come due to the availability of stronger medications and additional treatment options for treating hepatotropic viruses that cause liver problems. Hospital admissions attributable to alcohol-associated hepatitis (AH) are on the rise in tandem with a significant rise in healthcare costs and utilization [9]. The most severe form of alcoholic liver disease,

alcoholic hepatitis has a significant cost, morbidity, and death impact. But for the last almost three decades, the available treatments for severe alcoholic hepatitis (Maddrey's discriminant score > 32) have remained mostly unchanged. The only recognized treatments for severe alcoholic hepatitis are still nutrition therapy, steroids, and pentoxifylline [10]. When compared to either drug alone, there is no benefit to combining or sequencing pentoxifylline and steroids [11]. Patients with severe alcoholic hepatitis who are not sensitive to steroids (Lille score > 0.45) have no therapeutic choices. Significant advancements in the treatment of severe alcoholic hepatitis are probably in store thanks to developments in the basic sciences and a growing knowledge of the pathophysiology of alcoholic liver disease. Aspects of the pathophysiology and targeted treatment options for people with alcoholic liver disease are covered in this overview.

EPIDEMIOLOGY:

Particularly in the US, where liver biopsies are rarely done for this ailment, the epidemiology of AH is not well studied. However, trends in alcohol consumption habits indicate that the incidence of AH is expected to rise in Western countries. Higher alcohol consumption rates have been noted in recent US reports on the effects of state alcohol sales laws [12]. Additionally, binge drinking practices have risen dramatically over the past ten years, and drinking at an earlier age has increased as well. The death rate from alcoholic liver disease has increased as a result of these behaviours; among all age groups, Americans aged 25 to 34 had the highest increase in liver-related mortality between 2009 and 2016, with alcoholic liver disease being the sole cause of this increase. The epidemiology of AH has not been thoroughly investigated in any US studies, despite the fact that AH is probably responsible for a sizable percentage of these deaths. The prevalence of AH increased from 24 to 34 per million women and from 37 to 46 per million males between 1999 and 2008, according to Danish national cohort research [13]. It is probable that comparable patterns have been seen in other Western countries.

The health-care and financial burden of AH has grown throughout the past ten years due to the shifting epidemiology of alcohol use and alcohol-related liver disease. For instance, from 2002 to 2010, the Nationwide Inpatient Sample showed higher hospitalization rates for AH. Although the inpatient mortality rate decreased significantly as a result of AH (4.3% absolute risk reduction), hospitalization costs increased by 41% [10]. The inpatient costs of care for alcoholic cirrhosis increased by 96% between 2002 and 2014, accounting for nearly half of all cirrhosis

www.shutterstock.com - 1337938682

[14] inpatient expenses, according to another analysis. For both cases, the length of stay stayed constant over the study period, hence higher expenses most likely indicate an absolute increase in resource use.

PATHIPHYSIOLOGY:

Alcohol's effects both inside and outside the liver are what cause AH. Both inducible (CYP2E1) and non-inducible (alcohol dehydrogenase) enzymes break down alcohol in hepatocytes to produce the hazardous metabolite acetaldehyde. Apart from acetaldehyde, CYP2E1 produces a number of reactive oxygen intermediates (ROIs). Hepatocyte injury results in the release of damage-associated molecular patterns (DAMPs), and acetaldehyde directly causes hepatocyte mortality through both necrosis and apoptosis. Alcohol's effects both inside and outside the liver are what cause AH. Both inducible (CYP2E1) and non-inducible (alcohol dehydrogenase) enzymes break down alcohol in hepatocytes to produce the hazardous metabolite acetaldehyde. Apart from acetaldehyde, CYP2E1 produces a number of reactive oxygen intermediates (ROIs). Hepatocyte injury

the expression of tight-junction proteins, increasing intestinal mucosal permeability and allowing pathogen-associated molecular patterns (PAMPs) like lipopolysaccharide (LPS) to translocate into the liver. including DAMPs, PAMPs can then trigger macrophage inflammasomes through TLR, which results in the production of many inflammatory cytokines (including IL-1 β , TNF- α , and IL-10) and neutrophil chemokines (like IL-8, Gro- α , CXCL-5, and CXCL-6). The overall rise in intra-hepatic inflammation feeds back into hepatic failure, ROI formation, and further hepatocellular mitochondrial dysfunction. Liver failure in AH is primarily caused by dysregulated hepatic inflammation, but there are also some clinical findings that suggest hepatocellular dysfunction and delayed regeneration. Hepatocyte proliferation is nearly completely lost in liver explants

results in the release of damage-associated molecular patterns (DAMPs), and acetaldehyde directly causes hepatocyte mortality through both necrosis and apoptosis. After DAMPs attach to Toll-like receptors (TLRs) in Kupffer cells, the liver's resident tissue macrophage, the inflammasome—a multiprotein complex that contains caspase 1—becomes active. The cytokine interleukin 1 beta (IL-1 β) is produced by caspase 1 in response to inflammasome activation [15]. Alcohol has harmful effects on the intestines, which ultimately cause inflammation in the liver through a variety of ways. In particular, alcohol damages intestinal epithelial cells directly and reduces

from AH patients undergoing LT, in contrast to those with alcoholic cirrhosis and normal livers [16]. Additionally, in severe AH 20, hepatocyte growth is linked to better survival. The failure of liver progenitor cells (LPCs) to differentiate into mature hepatocytes is associated with a lower survival rate, and patients with AH show a notable proliferation of LPCs (referred to as ductular response). The molecular pathways of hepatocellular dysfunction in AH were further outlined by Argemi *et al.* discovered that the development of AH was typified by impaired activity of liver-enriched transcription factors after performing untargeted RNA sequencing in livers with various

alcoholic liver disease phenotypes. One of the main transcriptional regulators in AH was transforming growth factor beta 1 (TGF- β 1), which also caused fetal isoforms of the hepatic nuclear factor 4a (HNF-4a) P2 promoter, which led to impaired hepatic metabolic and synthetic function. Epigenetic processes were responsible for the altered expression of genes that depend on HNF-4a. All of these data point to the importance of hepatocellular dysfunction, poor regeneration, and intra-hepatic inflammation in the pathophysiology of AH. Our understanding of alcoholic liver disease has recently been broadened by genetic predisposition. Certain pertinent genetic signals, such as hydroxysteroid 17-beta dehydrogenase, transmembrane superfamily member, and patatin-like phospholipase domain-containing protein, are shared with the non-alcoholic steatohepatitis counterpart. Mutations in CYP2E1 and, more recently, a transcriptome study were over-represented in AH or had prognostic implications nevertheless, the effect of genetic predisposition in AH is less evident. The latter enhanced the model for end-stage liver disease (MELD) and the prediction of transplant-free survival by identifying a 123-gene prognostic signature from fixed liver biopsy samples in patients with severe AH. Hepatic stellate cells, intermediary metabolism, and oxidative stress and inflammatory pathways were all associated with the detected genetic markers. Alcoholic liver disease is one of the chronic liver diseases whose pathophysiology has been linked to gut dysbiosis. Alcohol causes changes in bacterial communities favouring pathogenic species in both human and mouse investigations, and it directly leads to gut microbial dysbiosis. Since a recent translational study shown that severe AH patients had increased anti-fungal immune responses and decreased fungal diversification, non-bacterial species are also impacted. The gut-liver axis is upset by these microbiota changes, either directly through bacterial metabolites or indirectly through TLRs and other signalling molecules (PAMP/DAMP pathways) and immune system activation [17]. The positive benefits that intestinal flora manipulation has on AH patients, as seen in pilot studies employing either rifaximin or faecal microbiota transplantation, provide more proof that the gut-liver axis and gut eubiosis are important therapeutic targets.

DIAGNOSIS:

A patient with prolonged alcohol consumption who presents with liver disease should always have AH diagnosed. Abdominal imaging, blood cultures, ascitic fluid investigation, urine and culture, and chest X-rays should all be done because the clinical presentation of AH can resemble sepsis or cholangitis.

(Lucey and colleagues, 2009; Singal and colleagues, 2014b) It's also important to take into account decompensation of alcoholic liver disease from sources other than AH and other liver illnesses. Jaundice lasting longer than three months, transaminases over 400 IU/l, and a history of alcohol consumption more than four weeks before presentation are all considered atypical symptoms of AH. The clinical diagnosis of AH may be made with the aid of the platelet and white blood cell counts. Hardy et al. (2013) However, liver biopsies may be necessary for 25–30% of AH patients in order to make a correct diagnosis, particularly in cases where the clinical diagnosis is still unclear.

(Petts et al., 2015, O'Shea et al., 2010b). Mallory bodies, ballooning degeneration with hepatocyte necrosis or apoptosis, and lobular inflammation with neutrophilic infiltration are histological findings in a typical AH patient. Perivenular fibrosis, ductular stasis of bile or bilirubin stasis, and intrahepatic cholestasis are seen in more severe cases. Altamirano et al. (2014), Michelena et al. (2015), and Spahr et al. (2001) Fibrosis and steatosis are present in most patients to varied degrees.

Given the prevalence of coagulopathy and/or ascites in these patients, transjugular liver biopsy is advised. The wedge hepatic venous gradient and portal pressure, which are associated with patient survival and outcome, are likewise shown by the transjugular method. (Rincon & colleagues, 2007) Mega mitochondria, bilirubinostasis, neutrophilic infiltration, and steatosis grade are histological features that may help indicate how well AH patients will respond to corticosteroids. In addition to Mathurin et al. (1996), Altamirano et al. (2014), Shasthry et al. (2014), and Duvoux et al. (2004), Liver biopsies also

offer recommendations for patient selection for clinical trial enrolment. Hardy et al. (2013) and Petts et al. (2015) Measurements of mitochondrial bioenergetics in peripheral blood cells, evaluation of markers of liver progenitor cell proliferation, and doppler ultrasound examination of the liver for measurements on hepatic blood flow are examples of emerging diagnostic modalities (Han et al., 2002, Abhilash et al., 2015). (Sancho Bru et al., 2012; Singh et al., 2014a).

TREATMENT:

1. Abstinence from Alcohol:

To stop the progression of alcohol-related hepatitis, alcohol usage must be stopped immediately and for the rest of one's life. For each patient with alcoholic hepatitis, we work with our addiction specialists to customize a program of social and psychological support for abstinence. Although baclofen, a γ -aminobutyric acid (GABA) B-receptor agonist, has recently been shown to support short-term abstinence in a group of actively drinking patients with alcoholic cirrhosis, there are no studies that evaluate the effectiveness of drugs meant to lessen alcohol cravings in patients with alcoholic hepatitis [18]. Additionally, its safety profile is acceptable, in contrast to that of naltrexone or acamprosate, which have not been shown safe for use in treating patients with alcohol-related liver failure.

2. Corticosteroids:

By preventing transcription factors like NF- κ B and activator protein 1 (AP-1) from acting, corticosteroid therapy partially reverses the inflammatory process. Reduced levels of the proinflammatory cytokines interleukin-8 and TNF- α , soluble intracellular adhesion molecule 1 in hepatic venous blood, and intracellular adhesion molecule 1 expression on hepatocyte membranes are all signs of this effect in alcoholic hepatitis [19]. The conflicting results of individual trials and meta-analyses have made the use of corticosteroids to treat alcoholic hepatitis contentious. Corticosteroid use was not supported by a recent meta-analysis, but the authors did come to the conclusion that the evidence base is weakened by heterogeneous clinical studies that carry a significant risk of bias. Nevertheless, the same meta-analysis demonstrated that corticosteroids significantly decreased mortality in the subgroup of trials that included patients with hepatic encephalopathy or a Maddrey's discriminant function of at least 32 and that had a low risk of bias study design. The most popular corticosteroid treatment for alcoholic hepatitis is 40 mg of prednisolone daily for 28 days. Prednisolone can either be discontinued completely at the end of the term of treatment, or the dosage can be decreased

gradually over three weeks [20]. Hepatorenal syndrome, chronic hepatitis B virus infection, gastrointestinal bleeding, and a Maddrey's discriminant function of 32 or higher (or a MELD score of ≥ 21) without sepsis are among the conditions that call for treatment. To save one life, corticosteroid treatment is required for five patients. About 40% of people with alcoholic hepatitis, however, do not respond to corticosteroid therapy. In this subgroup, no other treatment—including pentoxifylline, which is discussed below—has been found to be successful. Patients having a Maddrey's discriminant function of less than 32 or a MELD score of less than 21 should not get corticosteroids until information is available to identify those who have a significant short-term risk of dying.

3. Liver Transplantation:

A period of abstinence will allow many patients to recover from alcoholic hepatitis, which has been deemed an absolute contraindication to liver transplantation since individuals with this condition have recently consumed alcohol. A patient with alcoholic hepatitis must now abstain for six months before they are eligible for transplantation under the majority of US transplant programs [21]. Sadly, a lot of patients pass away during this time, and those that survive with the best medical care will be identifiable long before six months have passed. According to Veldt et al., patients with alcoholic liver disease-related liver failure who do not get better within the first three months of quitting are not expected to live [22]. When treating an alcoholic patient with severe alcoholic hepatitis whose health worsens despite following abstinence, nutritional assistance, corticosteroids, and other aspects of medical therapy, liver transplantation hospitals are faced with a conundrum. Another worry is a resurgence of alcohol consumption following transplantation.

4. Anti-oxidants:

Multiple modes of cellular injury in alcoholic hepatitis result in hepatocyte oxidative injury, including toxic ethanol metabolites, inflammatory cell-mediated cytotoxicity, as well as mitochondrial and proteasome dysfunctions. Given the central role of oxidative injury in the pathogenesis of alcoholic hepatitis, the use of anti-oxidants in alcoholic hepatitis has garnered much attention. Unfortunately, as a group, anti-oxidants have largely failed to demonstrate a significant mortality benefit although a few treatments showed promise. One common antioxidant used to treat acute liver injury is N-acetylcysteine (NAC). NAC infusion plus prednisolone was shown to reduce mortality after 30 days in a randomized control trial when compared to prednisolone alone; however, this effect was not observed at the primary endpoint of 3 months [23].

Another research that used both GCSF and NAC did not demonstrate any improvement in outcomes over GCSF alone. Metadoxine is another antioxidant that shows promise in treating alcoholic hepatitis. It is believed to raise the levels of glutathione in the liver. Metadoxine is another promising antioxidant used to treat alcoholic hepatitis; it is believed to raise hepatic glutathione levels. In small open labelled studies, metadoxine combined with pentoxifylline or steroids increased survival at 3 and 6 months. Intriguingly, metadoxine-treated individuals achieved a greater rate of sobriety during this trial; this effect has also been noted in earlier retrospective assessments of alcohol dependence [24]. The simultaneous antioxidative and abstinence-maintenance qualities of metadoxine, along with a relatively good side-effect profile, make it an appealing therapeutic option for alcoholic hepatitis, provided that these qualities are validated in bigger investigations.

5. Anti-TNF- α Therapy:

Etanercept and infliximab are two anti-TNF- α medications that have been investigated as treatments for alcoholic hepatitis. Because of the promising outcomes of three small, early studies on infliximab—two nonrandomized and one randomized—a larger research was carried out to evaluate its effectiveness [25].

Patients with severe alcoholic hepatitis were the subjects of the ensuing randomized, controlled clinical trial, which examined the effects of intravenous infusions of infliximab plus prednisolone against placebo plus prednisolone (Maddrey's discriminant function, ≥ 32). However, due to a nonsignificant rise in mortality and a notable excess of serious infections in the infliximab cohort, the independent data and safety monitoring board terminated the trial early. It has been argued that the infliximab dosage (an intravenous infusion of 10 mg per kilogram of body weight administered three times daily on days 1, 14, and 28) is too high when compared to the single dose of 5 mg per kilogram that was employed in the other studies. In a small pilot study, etanercept seemed to improve the short-term survival of patients with alcoholic hepatitis however, a subsequent randomized, placebo-controlled trial by the same researchers revealed that the group receiving etanercept had a lower 6-month survival rate than the placebo group [26]. We believe that anti-TNF- α medications shouldn't be utilized to treat alcoholic hepatitis outside of clinical studies.

6. Nutritional Support:

Malnutrition affects all alcoholic hepatitis patients, and the degree of malnutrition is directly connected to the risk of death. Although it does not increase short-term survival, parenteral and enteral feeding improves

nutritional status [27]. In patients with severe alcoholic hepatitis, enteral tube feeding (2000 kcal per day) and prednisolone therapy (40 mg per day) were compared for 28 days in a randomized, controlled clinical trial. The two groups' survival rates at 28 days and 1 year were comparable, indicating that for certain individuals, nutritional therapy may be just as beneficial as corticosteroids.

CONCLUSION:

Better treatment options for viral liver illnesses are contributing to an increase in the prevalence of alcoholic hepatitis and the percentage of people with this condition. In recent decades, there has been no improvement in the morbidity, mortality, and The only effective therapy options available at the moment are nutrition, pentoxifylline, and steroids. Alcoholic hepatitis treatment options need to be improved and updated immediately. The pathophysiology of alcoholic hepatitis has been better understood thanks to developments in basic science, the "Omics" platform, and translational medicine. These developments have also created numerous novel therapy opportunities. Future clinical trials in the development of new therapies in the management of alcoholic hepatitis should concentrate on the following areas: improving liver regeneration by GCSF, targeting gut microbes and their products, targeting hepatic inflammation and infections through immune modulation, and early liver transplantation for those not responding to the standard of care (Figure 4). These are the most promising areas for research. With alcoholic hepatitis, conducting carefully planned and regulated clinical trials has historically been challenging because of a number of obstacles. Because study designs have become more standardized, the number of ongoing registered trials has increased exponentially, improving the situation. Currently, new treatments for alcoholic hepatitis are being tried that target dysbiosis, oxidative damage, inflammation, apoptosis, decreased regenerative capacity, alcohol use disorder, and disruption of the gut-liver axis. These treatments have enormous potential to enhance these patients' outcomes, whether used alone or in combination. For them to be accepted and incorporated into standard clinical practice, randomized clinical trials and additional methodical outcomes analysis would be necessary.

REFERENCES:

1. Alcohol-attributable deaths and years of potential life lost — United States, 2001. *MMWR Morb Mortal Wkly Rep* 2004; 53:866-70.
2. Mokdad AH, Marks JS, Stroup DF, Gerberding JL. Actual causes of death in the United States, 2000.

JAMA 2004;291: 1238-45. [Erratum, JAMA 2005;293:293-4.]

Vaillant GE. The natural history of alcoholism revisited. Boston: Harvard University Press, 1995.

4. Bellentani S, Saccoccio G, Costa G, et al. Drinking habits as cofactors of risk for alcohol induced liver damage. *Gut* 1997; 41:845-50.

5. Becker U, Deis A, Sørensen TI, et al. Prediction of risk of liver disease by alcohol intake, sex, and age: a prospective population study. *Hepatology* 1996;23: 1025-9.

6. de Alwis W, Day CP. Genetics of alcoholic liver disease and non-alcoholic fatty liver disease. *Semin Liver Dis* 2007; 27:44-54.

7. Nishiguchi S, Kuroki T, Yabusako T, et al. Detection of hepatitis C virus anti bodies and hepatitis C virus RNA in patients with alcoholic liver disease. *Hepatology* 1991; 14:985-9.

8. Teli MR, Day CP, Burt AD, Bennett MK, James OF. Determinants of progression to cirrhosis or fibrosis in pure alcoholic fatty liver. *Lancet* 1995; 346:987-90.

9. Naveau S, Giraud V, Borotto E, Aubert A, Capron F, Chaput JC. Excess weight risk factor for alcoholic liver disease. *Hepatology* 1997; 25:108-11.

10. Cohen JA, Kaplan MM. The SGOT/SGPT ratio — an indicator of alcoholic liver disease. *Dig Dis Sci* 1979; 24:835-8.

11. Vech RL, Lumeng L, Li TK. Vitamin B6 metabolism in chronic alcohol abuse: the effect of ethanol oxidation on hepatic pyridoxal 5'-phosphate metabolism. *J Clin Invest* 1975; 55:1026-32.

12. Ludwig S, Kaplowitz N. Effect of pyridoxine deficiency on serum and liver transaminases in experimental liver injury in the rat. *Gastroenterology* 1980; 79:545-9.

13. Matloff DS, Selinger MJ, Kaplan MM. Hepatic transaminase activity in alcoholic liver disease. *Gastroenterology* 1980;78: 1389-92.

14. Mutimer DJ, Burra P, Neuberger JM, et al. Managing severe alcoholic hepatitis complicated by renal failure. *Q J Med* 1993; 86:649-56.

15. Nagy LE: The Role of Innate Immunity in Alcoholic Liver Disease. *Alcohol Res.* 2015;37(2):237–50. [PMC free article] [PubMed] [Google Scholar]

16. Tian C, Stokowski RP, Kershenobich D, et al.: Variant in PNPLA3 is associated with alcoholic liver disease. *Nat Genet.* 2010;42(1):21–3. 10.1038/ng.488 [DOI] [PubMed] [Google Scholar]; F1000 Recommendation

17. Konturek PC, Harsch IA, Konturek K, et al. : Gut–Liver Axis: How Do Gut Bacteria Influence the Liver? *Med Sci (Basel).* 2018;6(3): pii: E79. 10.3390/medsci6030079 [DOI] [PMC free article]

[PubMed] [Google Scholar]; F1000 Recommendation.

18. Addolorato G, Leggio L, Ferrulli A, et al. Effectiveness and safety of baclofen for maintenance of alcohol abstinence in alcohol-dependent patients with liver cirrhosis: randomised, double-blind controlled study. *Lancet* 2007; 370:1915-22.

19. Spahr L, Rubbia-Brandt L, Pugin J, et al. Rapid changes in alcoholic hepatitis histology under steroids: correlation with soluble intercellular adhesion molecule-1 in hepatic venous blood. *J Hepatol* 2001; 35:582-9.

20. Imperiale TF, McCullough AJ. Do corticosteroids reduce mortality from alcoholic hepatitis? A meta-analysis of the randomized trials. *Ann Intern Med* 1990;113: 299-307.

21. Everhart JE, Beresford TP. Liver transplantation for alcoholic liver disease: a survey of transplantation programs in the United States. *Liver Transpl Surg* 1997;3: 220-6.

22. Veldt BJ, Lainé F, Guillygomarc'h A, et al. Indication of liver transplantation in severe alcoholic liver cirrhosis: quantitative evaluation and optimal timing. *J Hepatol* 2002; 36:93-8.

23. Nguyen-Khac E, Thevenot T, Piquet M-A, Benferhat S, Gorla O, Chatelain D, et al. Glucocorticoids plus N-Acetylcysteine in Severe Alcoholic Hepatitis. *New England Journal of Medicine.* 2011;365(19):1781–9. [PubMed: 22070475].

24. Leggio L, Kenna GA, Ferrulli A, Zywiak WH, Caputo F, Swift RM, et al. Preliminary findings on the use of metadoxine for the treatment of alcohol dependence and alcoholic liver disease. *Hum Psychopharmacol.* 2011;26(8):554–9. [PubMed: 22095793].

25. Mookerjee RP, Sen S, Davies NA, Hodges SJ, Williams R, Jalan R. Tumour necrosis factor alpha is an important mediator of portal and systemic haemodynamic derangements in alcoholic hepatitis. *Gut* 2003; 52:1182-7.

26. Boetticher NC, Peine CJ, Kwo P, et al. A randomized, double-blinded, placebo controlled multicentre trial of etanercept in the treatment of alcoholic hepatitis. *Gastroenterology* 2008; 135:1953-60.

27. Stickel F, Hoehn B, Schuppan D, Seitz HK. Nutritional therapy in alcoholic liver disease. *Aliment Pharmacol Ther* 2003; 18:357-73.

28. Cabré E, Rodríguez-Iglesias P, Caballeria J, et al. Short- and long-term outcome of severe alcohol-induced hepatitis treated with steroids or enteral nutrition: a multicentre randomized trial. *Hepatology* 2000; 32:36-42.